

The Role of Organizational Support in Moderating the Influence of Learning Agility on Employee Performance

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Article history:

Received October 08, 2022; Accepted: December 30, 2022; Displayed Online: January 26, 2023; Published: June 30, 2022

Keywords

Learning Agility;
Organizational Support;
Customer Service;
Employee Performance;

Abstract

This research aims to find out; (1) whether learning agility affects the performance of customer service, (2) whether organizational support affects customer service performance, and (3) whether organizational support able to moderate the relationship between learning agility and customer service performance. The research method used in this research is a descriptive survey and an explanatory survey. The population in this study was 120 customer service employees spread across government and private banking institutions in Kupang City. The number of samples is 92 customer service people. The sampling technique used is simple random sampling. This study uses multivariate statistical analysis, Moderated Regression Analysis (MRA). The results of the study show that 1) learning agility has a positive and significant effect on customer service performance, (2) organizational support has a positive and significant effect on customer service performance, and (3) organizational support can moderate the relationship between learning agility and customer service performance. Increasing organizational support to its employees will strengthen the causal relationship between learning agility and performance.

1. Introduction

The current condition of the Covid-19 pandemic has an impact of uncertainty on every business sector, including the banking sector. This condition requires every business organization in the

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banking industry to be able to adapt to this condition. Business organizations are required to make changes in the organization management system in order to increase productivity. These great demands have resulted in the management of business organizations having to work more optimally in managing all aspects they have effectively and efficiently. One aspect is human resources which is the driving force of the organization. Human resources are the most important assets in an organization because they are the resources that run and control, and develop the organization in the midst of changing demands. Rivai and Sagala (2009) say that the aspect of human resources, in this case, qualified employees and meeting performance standards, will greatly determine the progress of a business organization.

There is a close relationship between individual performance and organizational performance. If employee performance is good, organizational performance will likely be good and vice versa. Furthermore, Wilkovich and Boudreau (1999) say that the performance shown by employees will reflect the success or failure of an organization, so that employee performance is the most important employee characteristic to pay attention to.

Customer service is an activity carried out by employees to provide services to customers. Customer service employees are the spearhead of a banking institution in terms of providing services. Good or bad services provided by customer service employees will impact these banking institutions. Kasmir (Ifari, 2021) says that customer service employees must meet physical and mental requirements, personality and social requirements.

Many factors determine whether or not the optimal performance of an employee. Learning agility is one of the factors that can determine a person's performance (Gravett, 2016). The same thing was also stated by Howard (2017), Dries, Vantilborgh, & Peppermans (2012), Ifari (2021), and Santoso and Yuzarion (2021).

Another factor that also influences whether or not an employee's performance is good or bad is organizational support (Arshadi & Hayayi, 2013). Osman et al. (2010) also said that organizational support can influence employee performance. According to Eisenberger and Rhoades (2001), organizational support refers to employees' perceptions of the extent to which the organization values their contributions and cares about their well-being. Employees expect care from the organization for what they have done.

This study's objectives are to determine the following: 1) Does Learning Agility affect customer service performance? 2) Does organizational support affect customer service performance? 3) Can organizational support moderate the relationship between Learning Agility and customer service performance?

2. Materials and Methods

Learning Agility

Learning Agility (Hallenbeck, 2016) is a key factor that distinguishes those who can extract the most learning from any experience and then apply it. Furthermore, it is also said that *learning agility* is one of the factors that make a difference in an employee's career success (Hallenbeck, 2016). Another opinion about *learning agility* was put forward by Gravett (2016), who stated that learning agility is the learning ability of an employee related to adaptability and willingness to face the unknown and is also used to predict a person's performance in doing new tasks. Further said by De Meuse et al. (2010) that everyone who has high *learning agility* will take appropriate lessons from their experiences and apply those lessons to new situations. People with high *agile learning* seek new challenges, actively seek feedback from others so they can grow and develop, tend to *self-reflect*, evaluate their experiences and draw practical conclusions. Measurement of learning agility uses the

dimensions proposed by Eichinger & Lombardo (Jatmika & Puspitasari, 2019), which consist of mental agility, change agility, people agility, and results agility.

Perceived organizational support - POS

According to Eisenberger and Rhoades (2001), *Perceived organizational support* (POS) refers to employees' perceptions of the extent to which the organization values their contributions and cares about their well-being. Eisenberger *et al.* (2011) state that employees perceive their work as a reciprocal relationship that reflects a relative dependence that goes beyond a formal contract with the organization, which means that employees and the organization are involved in a reciprocal relationship.

Measurement of organizational support refers to the measures proposed by Eisenberger *et al.* (1990) and Boateng (2014 and 2018), including; 1) caring, 2) welfare, and 3) assistance and benefits.

Employee performance

Performance is a form of work produced by someone (Robbins & Judge, 2016). Another definition is that performance is what employees do and don't do, which consists of the quality of work, the quantity of work, timeliness, supervision, and cost efficiency (Langton, Robbins, & Judge, 2013). August W. Smith (Sedarmayanti, 1995) said that performance is "... output drive from processes, human or otherwise". Performance is the result or output of a process.

In this study, to measure the performance of customer service employees, researchers used an instrument developed from the indicators proposed by Ruky (2004), including employee abilities, discipline, and services provided.

Previous Research

Several previous studies examined the effect of *Learning Agility* on employee performance, among others; Howard, D. (2017). Dries, N., Vantilborgh, T., & Peppermans, R. (2012), Ifari, Alde Rahman, 2021, and Ayu Meryka Santoso and Yuzarion, 2021. Their results show that *learning agility* has a causal relationship with performance. The better *Learning agility* you have will lead to an increase in employee performance.

The study by Arshadi and Hayayi (2013) showed that organizational support improved employee performance at the National Iranian Drilling (NIDC) company. The study of Osman *et al.* (2010) concluded that organizational support was able to influence employee performance and personality in 723 *frontline hotel employees* in Turkey. Organizational support refers to employees' perceptions of the extent to which the organization values their contributions and cares about their well-being. Employees expect care from the organization for what they have done.

Research Hypothesis

Based on the description above, the formulation of the hypothesis in this study is 1) Learning agility has a positive effect on customer service performance, 2) Organizational support affects customer service performance, and 3) Organizational support can moderate the effect of Learning agility on customer service performance.

Research Method

This study uses a quantitative approach. The research method used in this research is a descriptive survey and an explanatory survey. The descriptive survey method is used to make a systematic, factual, and accurate description, picture, or painting of the facts, characteristics, and relationships between the investigated phenomena. At the same time, the explanatory survey method is used to determine the relationship between variables by testing hypotheses through statistical data processing and testing (Nazir, 2000).

The data source comes from a sample of 92 government bank customer service people in Kupang- Indonesia. Data analysis used Moderated Regression Analysis (MRA) with the help of SPSS Version 20. Ghazali (2015) says that the MRA moderation regression analysis is a multiple regression where the regression equation contains elements of interaction or multiplication between independent variables.

3. Results and Discussions

Based on the results of descriptive data analysis, it is known that customer service employees of several banks in the city of Kupang have high learning agility (3.78) in terms of the ability to extract more learning from experience and then apply it, adaptability, willingness to face things that are difficult. Unknown in terms of doing new tasks, the ability to learn from others to grow and develop, evaluate their experiences and draw practical conclusions. Customer service employees have a good perception (3.66) about organizational support, in this case, care, welfare, assistance, and benefits provided by the bank to them. Bank customer service employees also have good performance (3.99) in terms of ability, discipline, and service provided to customers.

The results of data processing to test the proposed hypothesis used a multivariate analysis statistical tool, namely Moderated Regression Analysis (MRA). A summary of the results of data processing (MRA analysis output) from each stage can be seen in table 1 below.

Table 1
MRA Output Summary Table

Mathematical Models	Unstandardized Coefficients	Adjusted R Square	Sig
1. CS Performance = a + b1 Learning Agility	CS Performance = 6.391 + 0.370 Learning Agility	0.137 (13.7%)	0.000
2. CS Performance = a + b1 Learning Agility + b2 Organizational Support + b3 Learning Agility*Organizational Support	CS Performance = 10,710 + 0.225 Learning Agility + 0.163 Organizational Support + 0.139 Learning Agility*Organizational Support	0.226 (22.6%) 0.220 (22.0%)	0.002 0.007

Based on the results of data processing summarized in the table above, a discussion of the relationship between learning agility, organizational support, and customer service employee performance can be presented below.

Causal Relationship Learning Agility and Customer Service Performance

The results of statistical tests prove the significant effect of learning agility on customer service performance, where the p-value (Sig) is smaller than the specified alpha (α) value ($0.000 < 0.05$). The results of this test mean that the increase or decrease in the performance of CS employees in several banks in Kupang City is influenced or determined by their learning agility.

The regression coefficient of the causal relationship between learning agility (X_1) and CS employee performance (Y) is positive at 0.370. This positive causal relationship means that learning agility positively influences the performance of CS employees in several banks in Kupang City. If there is an increase in the learning agility variable, it will affect the increase in the CS employee performance variable. The contribution of the influence of learning agility to changes in the performance of CS employees is 13.7%.

The test results above show that learning agility is formed by the ability to extract more learning from any experience and then apply it, adaptability, willingness to face the unknown in terms of doing new tasks, and ability to learn from others to grow and develop. Developing and evaluating their experiences and drawing practical conclusions will be able to affect the performance of CS employees in several banks in Kupang City, which is indicated by the increase in employee skills, discipline, and services provided to customers. The results of this study are in accordance with research conducted by Howard, D. (2017). Dries, N., Vantilborgh, T., & Peppermans, R. (2012), Ifari, Alde Rahman, 2021, and Ayu Meryka Santoso and Yuzarion, 2021. Their results say that learning agility has a causal relationship with performance. The better Learning agility you have will lead to an increase in employee performance.

Causal Relationship of Organizational Support and Customer Service Performance.

The results of statistical tests prove the significant effect of organizational support on customer service performance, where the p-value (Sig) is smaller than the specified alpha (α) value ($0.002 < 0.05$). The results of this test have the meaning that the increase or decrease in the performance of CS employees in several banks in Kupang City is influenced or determined by the organizational support that they perceive.

The regression coefficient of the causal relationship between organizational support (X_2) and CS employee performance (Y) is positive at 0.163. This positive causal relationship means that organizational support positively influences the performance of CS employees in several banks in Kupang City. If there is an increase in employee perceptions of organizational support, it will increase their performance. The contribution of the influence of organizational support to changes in the performance of CS employees is 22.6%.

The test results above show that employees' perceptions of organizational support in terms of concern, welfare, as well as assistance and benefits provided by the organization will be able to affect the performance of CS employees in several banks in Kupang City, which is indicated by the increase in employee capabilities, discipline, and services provided to customers.

The results of this study are in accordance with research conducted by Arshadi and Hayayi (2013), which showed that organizational support was able to improve employee performance at the National Iranian Drilling (NIDC) company. The study of Osman et al. (2010) concluded that organizational support is able to influence the performance of frontline hotel employees in Turkey.

The Role of Organizational Support in Moderating the Effect of Learning Agility on Employee Performance

The results of statistical tests prove the significant effect of organizational support as a moderating causal relationship between learning agility and customer service performance, where the p-value (Sig) is smaller than the specified alpha (α) value ($0.007 < 0.05$). This shows that organizational support is able to play a role in moderating the causal relationship between learning agility and customer service performance.

The regression coefficient for organizational support as a moderating causal relationship between learning agility and customer service performance is positive at 0.139. This positive regression coefficient means that if there is an increase in the value of the interaction between learning agility and organizational support, it will increase or strengthen the causal relationship between learning agility and CS employee performance. This is evident in the interaction between learning agility and organizational support. There is an increase in the contribution of the influence of learning agility on the performance of CS employees, from 13.7% to 22.0%.

To improve employee performance, high learning agility is needed from employees and also organizational support in terms of care, welfare, assistance, and benefits provided by the organization. In facing the competition in the banking industry in Kupang City, all factors must be considered properly by each CS in carrying out their duties and roles, as well as banking leaders in supporting their employees. Factors that increase learning agility and organizational support are important in improving employee performance, especially CS.

4. Conclusion

The results of the study show that: 1) Customer service employees of several banks, especially in Kupang City, have a high level of learning and high agility, have a good perception of the organizational support they feel, and have good performance. 2) Increasing Learning agility owned by employees will be able to improve the performance of customer service employees at banking institutions in Kupang City. 3) Organizational support The better terms of care, welfare, as well as assistance, and benefits provided by the organization will be able to improve the performance of CS employees in several banks in Kupang City. 4) Organizational support can moderate the effect of learning agility on the performance of customer service employees of several banks in Kupang City.

Based on the conclusion, some suggestions are proposed as follows. 1) Banking institutions are expected to continue to increase support for their employees in terms of care, welfare, as well as assistance, and benefits. With support from the organization, it is hoped that employees will continue to improve their learning agility and performance. 2) Banking institutions must strive to encourage an increase in the learning agility of employees because the increase in learning agility will also have an impact on increasing their performance. 3) Banking institutions must continue to increase their support for employees because the better employees' perception of the support provided by the organization makes them feel motivated to improve their performance. 4) To improve the performance of its employees, the banking sector must continue to pay attention to improving the learning agility of each employee properly. The attention and support from the bank leadership for the needs and welfare of employees will have an effect on increasing employee performance.

Acknowledgments

We do thank all the reviewers and also professional editors who have contributed to this manuscript so that this manuscript can be accepted.

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